

DESCRIPTION SPECIFIC TO DESCRIPTIVE LYRICS
AESTHETIC SIGNIFICANCE OF MEANS

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Abstract: This article talks about the aesthetic significance of descriptive means, about the varieties of means of descriptive lyrics, in the example of poems by the modern Uzbek poetess Oydin Khojiyeva.

Key words: Descriptive lyrics, descriptive object, lyrical subject and object, poet's point of view, lyrical situation.

Introduction

The diversity of descriptive expression typical of descriptive lyric visions extends the possibilities of characterization in poetry somewhat. Because the nature, thing-thing, state, phenomenon, concept that is made an object in the poem in some cases, even the character serves to move the subjective state as the object of description. According to the definitions of literary scholars, poetry belonging to descriptive lyricism is a static embodiment of events – phenomena of the outer world, that is, the opening of the inner world of that subject is expected through the description of some kind, usually nature, that attracts the attention of the lyrical subject. Reading and observing the belonging of today's examples of poetry to descriptive lyricism, I am sure that not only a description of nature is expressed, but also a subjective universe, through the means of diverse descriptive objects, as we have already mentioned.

The main of the result

Although the musings, experiences, and experiences of the “lyrical men” characteristic of the nature of descriptive lyricism are not directly expressed, “the descriptive details in lyrical works are generally considered important as an object of emotion”. In descriptive lyricism, the direct expression of emotions tends to a

minimum, the sensations of the subject are the object (thing, Event, state, event, person v.b.) is expressed by description. From these theoretical definitions, it follows that since descriptive lyricism has its place in the representation of the object of emotion in any case, then a lyrical description is given by the way the descriptive tool is directly expressed by emotion or metaphorically expressed by the related concepts of the descriptive object. The literary scholar Ulugbek Hamdamov comments on this: “the figurative-metaphorical appearance of descriptive lyrics in terms of expression, as well as the non-figurative appearance, are also common” .¹ While the lyrics differ in the scope of the topic depending on the philosophical, landscape, types of love, they represent a descriptive tool of the nature of metaphoricity that serves to reveal the topic in them.

Because it is natural that descriptive means cannot be delimited by expressing the colorful and turfosities of poetic themes in one or two thirst, that is, the variety of descriptive means in poetry and the meeting of original manifestations not found in the creativity of another in each creator is a poetic invention as a find. Just as an artist creates a new and unique example in the color palette of works of the landscape, still life, portrait or other genre, the poet is able to show what the possibilities of the description of a lyrical work are, because of how skillfully he was able to use his fantasy, vocabulary. We turn to some lyrical works in order to justify our thoughts.

There are many examples of descriptive lyrics in the work of the Uzbek poet Aydin Hajiyeva. In the poem "Sado bergil", the state as a means of childhood longing description continues to be the object, that is, the state is being portrayed by the expression of the feeling of longing:

My playful childhood,
No information.

¹ Поспелов Г. Лирика среди литературных родов.- М.: Изд-во Московского Ун-та. 1976. –С.106.
Қуронов Д., Мамажонов З., Шералиева М. Адабиётшунослик луғати. – Тошкент: akademnashr, 2013. –Б.77.
Quronov D. Adabiyot nazariyasi asoslari. – Т.: Navoiy universiteti; 2018. –В.389.
Улугбек Ҳамдам. Янги ўзбек шеърляти. – Т.: Адиб, 2012. – Б.261.

Did you not return - a, or touched

A stray bullet?

By nature, the fact that childhood does not return is obvious to everyone, but the Desolation of childhood, which passed through the poet's eyes, is seen as a phenomenon with its own reason, while looking for a childhood that went without a ravine, the poet imagines that he was missing by being shot, and tries to give a reason:

Fast sniper bow

Have you come across?

How many years my eyes are on the way

Don't bring voice

My playful childhood,

My playful childhood![3;90]

Observing the text of the poem, The described object is openly exclaimed by an appeal in the last two paragraphs presented above: no information, my playful childhood. In the four clauses that precede these clauses, the word childhood is not mentioned, while the longing for Childhood, the feeling of nostalgia in the first three clauses give us a clear picture of event-state, the word remains unopened as to what it is going about:

From which river tributary

Are you watering?

In the Lightning of the rock

Are you going?

Mehrigio in the forests

Were you?

Like a new moon in the heavens

Are you full?

Into the cup of the carpenter

Have you been?

To the colors of the rainbow

Have you settled?[2;45]

In the first verses of the poem, The object is depicted, and in the following paragraphs the descriptive object uses the opportunity to speak directly, the poet Aydin Hajiyeva shows his unique style in creating examples of descriptive lyrics.

But we notice a gesture that brings sweet memories to our memory, that is, in the drawing of memories that remind us of the next one busy childhood, the description is manifested by the image of childhood longing:

Towards the village returning to the herd

Serka.

Cheerful wind

With the blind...

Are you watering?, Are you going?, Are you?, Are you full?, Have you been?, Have you settled?, Either touched a hit bullet?, Have you ever encountered? rhetorical inquiries, such as the description of the case, are poetically actualized with a tone to describe the childhood longing and memories that the poet Awakens in the moment in his heart.

It is worth mentioning another component that moves the elements of the description in the poem - the position that the title also occupies. The title of the poem is a small tool for the artistic intention of the creator and the expressiveness of the idea of the work, and this tool takes its place from the very beginning of the compositional construction of the work. Therefore, we can say that while ensuring the construction of the text in the load of the title, the content will bring the text of the work to the surface. Aydin Hajiyeva's choice of title to the poem "Sado bergil" logically justifies itself in opening the content of the poem. Because even though the poem's text does not originally refer to "sado bergil", the lyrical hero is also enlivened in the title for the poetic description of the cry.

In the first verses of the poem, without the object being directly depicted, in the later paragraphs, examples of descriptive lyricism belonging to the description of the object representing the subject are found in many of Aydin Hajiyeva's poems. Poems"

visit“,” heaven olachalpak, John – olachalpak“,” peasant " can be evidence of our opinion. In the description of these sadness, the image of the event, the state is expressed. For example, in his poem known as” the visit”, early Moss landscapes form the leitmotive of the nature of the Fatherland.

“The skill of each poet is judged by the fact that he is able to acquire originality, determined by how he can use traditional arts, the image.” Since the immortal theme of the nature of the Motherland is sung in new images and descriptions in each creator's sad, new landscapes of the lyric of every time nature are drawn. In this respect we meet originality in the poem “visit " by Aydin Hajiyeva as well. That is, the description and description of the beautiful landscapes of the nature of the motherland in the early spring period are considered examples of descriptive lyrics, which have a significant place in the poetry of the 20th century, while Aydin Hajiyeva, continuing this tradition, will witness that the object of the description strives from tradition to novelty. Behind the image of a natural landscape, the poet invents his lyrical subject experiences – the feeling of love for the motherland-to the hearts:

The kite hits the Vulture whip,
It blooms Thunder.
Lightning to the heart...
Needle tongues of grass Bakhshi,
He will say, " go to the rain and die."
Oh, life is a miracle, vitality is good,
Light poured into the bottom of the tongue.

“Life is a miracle, vitality is good, light poured into the depths of the heart," to the poet's confession, the reader will also enjoy the depths of his own heart. Behind the image of the natural landscape, the poet indulges his lyrical subject experiences – the feeling of love for the motherland-to the hearts.

The lyrical description of this poem is also not directly mentioned in the phenomenon itself, which, as we have already mentioned, is the object of description.

On the contrary, we find this function of the description in the following verses, respectively:

Earth's delights-mushrooms

Spring holds his shoulders breast.

Rust rabbits from a thousand peat colors

Tie to the floor of the bride around.

The fact that the lyrical supper begins to delight the reader in a high Paphos conveys an early spring visit before our eyes.

Since associative units reminiscent of cabbage tarot, such as "earth shakes","Spring yels"," butterfly ground", do not feel the need to mention that the description is exactly spring. The phrase" The Prodigy who left the paints that were not in the Attor box to the malic steppes "as well as the phrase " the mother at the head of the Cradle is charming, the same soil with bone, the spring Homeland!"the poetess, impressed by her imagination and the beauty that appears before her eyes, dips into the poem in beautiful charms. The nature of this same homeland becomes realistic through the epithet "Spring Homeland". Ultimately, the expression of the spring homeland is evaluated as a novelty as an original find. Poems like this we see from the author's use of the possibilities of descriptive lyrics with a special talent that there is a unique style of Aydin Hajiyeva when creating descriptive samples.

Conclusion

In the conclusion of our thoughts, we want to say that descriptive lyrics open the door to a wide range of possibilities for the creator. Because the tool to be described is born from each creator's gaze, imagination, worldview, poetic perception of the environment and, of course, from his observability, sensitivity. Thus the ability of penmanship to individually meditative characterization is considered a process dependent on the ability to create original metaphors. The modern Uzbek poet Aydin Hajiyeva can serve as an example of a creator who created charming examples of descriptive lyrics in his poems.

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